

Can Opposition Parties Be Responsible?

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Opposition responsibility is a neglected field, and if at all noticed, opposition parties are often placed in the irresponsibility frame. The purpose of our paper is to examine to what extent, under which conditions, and in which ways opposition parties can be considered to act responsibly. This article will develop the concept of opposition responsibility and test the expectations in the behaviour of opposition parties in three countries: Hungary, Italy and Spain. The analysis highlights that opposition responsibility exceeds—although does not exclude—policy making and scrutiny activities as it has broader implications. We shall regard the opposition's general performance and their political system-related behaviour as components of responsibility.

Keywords: Opposition Performance, Quality Check, Democracy

1. Introduction—opposition responsibility in academic context

There are three major academic lines of thought that directly or indirectly refer to opposition parties' (ir)responsibility. Sartori's seminal work distinguished between the opposition that has a reasonable chance to govern and the permanent opposition that as such will never be in the position to govern. The latter expectedly will not have to respond that is it will not be accountable to the voters and will remain irresponsible as a result (Sartori, 1966, p. 35) while the governing parties will take the burden of responsibility for their decisions at the ballot box. This approach connects responsibility to accountability—the latter being a more direct action, taking place in an institutionalised form, at elections.

This distinction has been furthered by Mair's work (2011) in face of increased challenger party formation. Around the turn of the new millennium, new parties gained importance in several democracies that had had stable party system

patterns for decades. The claim was that while these parties appear attractive to the voters as they are responsive to voters' demands and represent them in their programmes, they are never made accountable—or indeed responsible as they are not in governing position.

A further development concerning the questions about opposition responsibility was related to the financial and economic crisis. At that time many governments were forced to take hard decisions to heal the crisis effects (De Giorgi and Moury, 2014). Still, the increased role of governments was accepted as they are aware of long term needs—as opposed the opposition parties that only advance the demands (Bardi et al., 2014, p. 237). In this perspective, responsibility contrasts with responsiveness, the latter being understood as a 'process in which politicians follow or even anticipate citizen opinion' (Esaiasson and Wlezien, 2017). Implicitly, opposition parties enforce merely voters' demands, have short-term perspectives and as such they are not the bearer of responsibility.

This sharp divide between responsibility and responsiveness and between governing and opposition forces requires further considerations, however. In the first place, the voters often make both government and opposition parties electorally responsible. Opposition parties can be blamed for governing failure even though governing positions and opposition positions offer different opportunities to affect political and policy outcome. This might particularly hit the temporary opposition parties that are part of the established party framework. Moreover, the sharp divide between established and challenger parties is not necessarily justified as many challenger parties would get into governing positions given the malleability of the old party frameworks. Thus, challenger parties should equally have vote, office and policy considerations to remain in the electoral competition. Lastly, as responsibility is ascribed to increased or even excessive government action opposition parties might have a function to maintain the standards of responsible government. Overall, on these grounds opposition responsibility can be duly expected.

To examine the possible responsibility components of opposition party behaviour we shall first develop the concept of opposition responsibility. This will be furthered by examining two possible aspects of responsible opposition behaviour, namely their performance and their role in checking the quality of responsible government. In the conclusion, we shall try to explain the emerging patterns of opposition responsibility in the three selected countries, Hungary, Italy and Spain.

2. Concept building and case selection

Opposition must fulfil certain functions like government scrutiny, participation in the legislative process and informing the voters with diverse publicity

instruments. If opposition refrains from these actions it would not fulfil its tasks: cannot criticise, cannot show alternatives, and cannot refer to the voters (Blondel, 1997). At the same time opposition should also ensure that its performance is accepted as legitimate (Dahl, 1966, p. xiii), that is the opposition is 'obliged' to ensure its legitimate position by maintaining the working conditions in parliament.

On these grounds we shall build the opposition responsibility concept around two aspects of opposition behaviour. First, we contend that the opposition parties should perform, what we shall call the *performance aspect* of opposition responsibility. The performance of opposition in parliament is an often-used measure to qualify party ability to fulfil its goals but a mere numerical aspect does not connect to respond automatically. Action is rightly expected but its optimal level is hard to decide. For example, low-key activity can be well explained with strategic political considerations. When for the opposition party the door to office seems wide open—prospectively in cooperation with those currently in government—political rationale does not purport heated opposition action. This low-key activity can be regarded as responsible as it might lead the party to office and thus the party could implement its electoral pledges. Similarly, and as a contrast, ostentatious activity is not necessarily responsible as it can lead to functional unbalance or can have reverse impact: proposing many bills or amendments without getting attention from voters or in parliament might not be responsible as not only parliaments have limited capacity to get involved simultaneously in multiple activities due to limitations of time, energy, funds or cognitive resources but also parliamentary parties, opposition among them. Still, in extreme cases excessive action even obstruction appears as part of responsible opposition behaviour in an attempt to serve a fundamental policy or political goal. So, to judge opposition responsible performance careful context-related analysis is necessary.

Second, the opposition should ensure their own legitimate working conditions—those being essential components of representative democracy. We shall call this behavioural aspect *quality check*. Responsible opposition is expected to verify that the fundamental functions of parliament remain intact and the work of the parliament is ensured. The executive normally enjoys superior position as compared to parliament and thus the capacity of opposition groups to check the quality of democracy is constrained. In the crisis environment, the governing parties apparently received entitlement to increase their terrain of action to fulfil long term responsibility. Nevertheless, governments might run the risk that under the pressure to make quick decisions they become less responsible as 'the temporal qualities of responsive and responsible politics' (Goetz, 2014, p. 384) are not observed. Regarding our theoretical frame whenever opposition protests against executive actions as their effects are not properly introduced or challenges urgency measures it acts in a responsible way. This is quality check per se.

The performance aspect and the quality check aspect are not a mere transcription or projection of the policy-related functions and the scrutiny functions of parliament, however. First of all, they cannot be separated from each other on functional grounds. For example, opposition might well initiate bills with the intention to defend the rules of the parliamentary game that is to do quality check. Also, performance and quality check cannot be translated into action or reaction per se. Possibly, performance has a larger component of action while quality check a larger component of reaction but both aspects of responsibility comprise action and reaction at the same time. For example a legislative initiative can well be a reaction to a government step, while quality defence momentums might not directly respond to government action. Generally, opposition does not only and simply react to government action but has an action potential on its own ground (De Giorgi and Ilonszki, 2018, p. 237). Moreover, opposition performance exceeds the numerical aspects of policy making and might well extend to the broader context with fundamental polity concerns.

The three selected country cases, Hungary, Italy and Spain offer the opportunity to follow up opposition responsibility on the above lines, on partisan, crisis related and polity aspects. First, the party systems have been substantially transformed in each country case: new challenger parties emerged; populist parties have gathered ground. Has this offered new responsibility patterns? Second, each country was hit hard by the economic crisis, thus excessive government action might have placed new challenges for the opposition parties. While the immediate effects of the crisis period have been examined with respect to each country (Ilonszki and Várnagy, 2014; Marangoni and Verzichelli, 2015; Palau et al., 2015) these were not placed in the responsibility frame. It also remains to be seen whether the need for quality check lasts beyond the immediate crisis period. As the opportunity structures of parliamentary opposition in Southern Europe both in terms of the scrutiny opportunities of the opposition and their opportunities to offer alternatives are very limited (Garritzmann, 2017) similarly to Hungary particularly since after 2010 this institutional similarity helps comparison.

Finally, each country faces a fundamental political challenge. In Hungary, increasing democracy deficit undermines the representative institutions for a decade now (Ágh, 2016; Lührman and Lindberg, 2019). In Italy, since the end of the First Republic, that is close to three decades now, the party system has gone through a process of profound renovation, without really finding a new equilibrium and stabilisation (Emanuele and Chiamonte, 2020). In Spain, politics have moved from bi-partisan consensus to increasing polarisation and confrontation and struggles to establish lasting, stable governments (Palau and Muñoz, 2018). While these challenges are different in kind (system related, party system related and government related) they raise substantive question for the opposition. Do opposition parties perform in parliament to maintain democratic

parliamentary rules of the game in Hungary? Do they play a constructive role in the formation of lasting party system patterns in Italy? Do they contribute to establish stable working governments in Spain?

As mentioned above neither the performance aspect nor the quality defence aspect can be ascribed to or connect to some straightforward numerical evidence. Adaptive performance that responds to the changing context and attentive quality check that responds to the challenges can be regarded as the foundations of responsible opposition party behaviour. On these grounds, we can formulate general, party-related and country-related expectations. In general terms, responsible opposition behaviour cannot be static—ideally an adjustment process is going on which is reflected both in performance and quality check; with regard to parties, we assume that opposition parties expectedly show varied responsibility patterns: although ‘permanent opposition status is not a direct or automatic indicator of party behaviour’ (De Giorgi and Ilonszki, 2018, p. 235), we shall expect more static behaviour from them as their status is more cemented (they are more stuck) than that of the temporary opposition parties; and we assume that party age might have an impact on opposition responsibility, with new parties primarily engaged with their own strategies and less inclined to adopt a responsible behaviour. Finally, we expect country differences particularly in terms of quality check: as the government pressure is the main trigger of opposition action in this regard the more government pressure on the representative institution will generate more responsible behaviour among opposition parties.

As the patterns of responsibility are mainly context driven, we shall focus on the cases independently. The next sections examine how opposition parties participate in these activities first focusing on the performance and then on the quality check aspects of their behaviour.

2.1 Opposition parties’ performance

In the theoretical section, we have referred to performance as one of the defining features of opposition. Would either their under-performance or excessive action curtail or undermine the working of the parliament? Would their activity hinder or promote the solution of fundamental policy and political issues? In this section, we aim to follow up opposition activity with these two large ‘responsibility considerations’ in mind covering the immediate pre-crisis period and the post-2010 decade.

In Hungary, in the 2006–2010 parliamentary period—that is one which over-arches the pre- and the first crisis years—opposition parties mainly showed non-responsible behaviour according to our conceptualisation. First, the liberal Alliance of Free Democrats (SzDSZ) quit the coalition government with the Socialists (Hungarian Socialist Party) its long time coalition partner due to policy

differences but also in face of the declining popularity of the Socialists and the lingering crisis. The SzDSz hoped to retain its electoral support with that step still remained an external supporter of the incoming minority government of the Socialists. The move did not pay as the liberals fell out of parliament at the 2010 elections, the party totally evaporated, and they also paved the way for populist takeover. Their quit did not serve party interest or government stability. The key opposition party actor was Fidesz, the large populist conservative party. It mobilised the street and proposed referendums that were even in contrast with the regulations of the Constitution as they were related to economic issues. Fidesz did not accept the proposition of the Socialist Prime Minister to work out a common anti-crisis strategy. At the same time, the party did not aim to take government responsibility during the crisis period: they did not demand early elections rather aimed to escalate the internal political turmoil. Further on Fidesz did not support the eventually established ‘quasi expert’ government that replaced the Socialist minority government in 2009. In fact, it seems that MDF was the only party among the opposition groups that in face of the crisis tried to play a responsible role to ensure government stability with their vote.

In addition to these political episodes the parliamentary scene clearly shows the declining activity of Fidesz. The number of initiated bills by the party diminished from 0.6 per MP to a mere 0.2 per MP (an all-time negative winner during parliamentary democracy in Hungary). The Fidesz’ satellite Christian Democratic People’s Party (KDNP) followed suite in parliamentary non-activity. Fidesz also lost the incentive to support government bills, this share fell from 45% to 33% from 2006 to 2010. The latter figure is particularly striking as this covers the period of the quasi expert government. We can rightly conclude that the main opposition party did not consider the solution of the crisis as a common goal, it substantially diminished its parliamentary presence and action, deepened conflict on the streets without claiming and acting for the party responsibility that is new elections. Under these heated conditions Fidesz gained a two-third constitutional majority at the 2010 elections, which it has maintained ever since. It seems that power-seeking non-responsible behaviour paid for the populist party.

Since after 2010 new opposition tendencies can be observed. The performance of the post-2010 opposition parties is substantially higher than that of the opposition parties before 2010 and has even increased between 2010 and 2018, that is in the past two parliamentary terms. The two new parties in opposition (the extreme right Jobbik and the green LMP) had a clear policy profile, which they wanted to ‘show’ and their strategic aim to get votes and make their policy visible well corresponded with their high-performance levels. The new opposition parties initially tried to establish consensual strategy towards Fidesz in an assumption that the governing party would need them as a partner, instead of the faceless Christian Democrats, or would support some of their initiatives. These hopes

have vanished in face of Fidesz' increasingly populist agenda, however. In terms of performance, the new opposition parties' responsibility frame is ambiguous: their high-level activity did not pay. The third opposition party, the Socialists, was less active after their election failure as they were disoriented in political and policy terms as well. Close to the end of our observation period Jobbik chose to move towards the centre and the three opposition parties began to work out common strategies among themselves particularly in scrutiny measures, a clear sign of responsibility in face of the populist governing party anti-democratic agenda.

In Italy, after the 2008 general elections, in a quasi bi-party system, the two main parties, the Democratic Party (PD) and the People of Freedom Party (a merger of Forza Italia [FI] and National Alliance) established by Berlusconi were able to control almost the 80% of seats at the Chamber of Deputies and more than 70% at the Senate. In contrast to the long-lasting equilibrium of the first Republic, government alternation¹ seemed feasible, which has naturally influenced the behaviour of opposition. Policy considerations and policy outputs became crucial determinants of political competition (Marangoni, 2013). To put it differently: in the new *output democracy* (Fabbrini, 2000), even opposition actors if they really aimed at succeeding could not be simply responsive but had to behave responsibly in promoting concrete and credible political and policy alternatives.

The crisis culminated in 2011 with the premature termination of the Berlusconi IV executive and the apparent stabilisation of the party system got to a halt. As a result, the responsibility of the opposition parties has been often explicitly invoked. First, this occurred at the formation of the Monti government in 2011, when the PD (formerly the opposition of the centre-right Berlusconi's executive) decided to join the oversized parliamentary majority giving birth to the technocratic executive that lasted until 2013 concluding with the emergence of new and challenging political actors such as, mainly, the 5 Stars Movement (M5S). Second, it was the case after the 2013 elections when, in the absence of a clear winner,² an executive was formed converging the main parliamentary forces (PD and FI again, among others). Furthermore, it was the case in 2019 when, after the crisis of the Northern League (NL)–M5S coalition, the PD decided to enter a governing coalition with M5S. In this case, responsibility has been evoked,

¹With the 'corollary' of the reform (or better, the reforms) of the electoral systems, and the substantive changes in the process of government formation (from pre-electoral to post-electoral coalitions).

²Neither one of the two main traditional coalitions nor the M5S had got the absolute majority of seats in both chambers.

so to say, in a more partisan way, by some political actors, explicitly to avoid early elections, and the likely victory of the populist and Eurosceptic Salvini's NL.

In terms of specific measures of parliamentary performance, no clear patterns seem to emerge. Between 2006 and 2016³ the small parties seem to be more active on both bill sponsorships and scrutiny activity. This can be explained, however, by the incentives, the MPs belonging to these parties might have (given the low number of available seats) to signal themselves as particularly active and effective to gain re-selection by their party leaderships (Marangoni and Russo, 2018). As a contrast both the M5S in 2014–2016 and the NL seem to perform relatively lower than other parliamentary groups in bills sponsorships. This confirms that these populist parties do not regard policy promotion and the parliamentary arena as their main focus and terrain of action. There seems to be, moreover (with some necessary prudence to be exerted in interpreting the data), an increasing relevance of parliamentary scrutiny. In the more recent legislative term under consideration here (2014–2016 during the Renzi government), the *per capita* number of (oral) interpellations has exceeded that of sponsored bills for all opposition parties, with the only partial exception of FI presenting the same average number of bills and interpellations per MP (1.8).⁴ In the new political context in the absence of bi-polar party system and with less clear and often fluid political alliances opposition parties, responsibly in a sense, started to orient their efforts towards the crucial function of legislative assemblies in contemporary parliamentary systems: being less concerned with 'making laws' and more with checking and scrutiny of the executive.

In Spain, during the 2008–2011 legislature, the Socialist (Partido Socialista Obrero Español [PSOE]) Zapatero government was under increasing pressure because of the unpopular policy measures it had to implement following EU recommendations. In this context, the main opposition party, the conservative Popular Party (PP), followed responsible behaviour showing less opposition to governmental initiatives compared with other opposition parties, mainly because of its high likelihood of entering into office at the next election and because most policy decisions of the government were in line with their policy preferences (Palau et al., 2015; Palau and Muñoz, 2018). While they did not vote against executive initiatives in large numbers, they introduced a significant number of legislative proposals in 2008–2011 to signal their policy preferences (the share increased

³Data source: digital archive of bills of the Italian Parliament (at www.senato.it) for the bills, and Italian Policy agendas' dataset (Borghetto et al., 2018) for the Interpellations.

⁴While the difference is rather evident in the cases of FdI (11 interpellations, against 8.2 bills, on average, per MP), NL (6.1 against 3.3), and also (although to a lesser degree) M5S (3.2 against 2.4).

from 0.2 to 0.6 bills per MP).⁵ The other opposition groups at that time, the far left (the Republican Left of Catalonia [ERC], United Left [IU] and Initiative for Catalonia Greens), the Catalan and the Basque nationalist parties (Convergence and Union [CIU] and the Basque Nationalist Party [PNV], respectively) also increased their performance introducing more parliamentary bills compared with previous legislatures. This increasing performance must be understood in the context of the economic crisis but also the minority status of the Zapatero government. At that time, a plurality of parties had the capacity to be pivotal, namely influence the parliamentary majority to pass bills. The literature has demonstrated that under these circumstances, parties are more likely to introduce bills (Brauninger and Debus, 2009). As a contrast, the scrutiny activity of opposition groups does not show a parallel increase, but this could be related to formal rules limiting the number of parliamentary questions and interpellations that opposition parties can introduce in Spain (see Chaqués et al., 2015, p. 90).

The two major facts in Spanish recent politics have been the declining electoral support of the two 'big' governing parties, PSOE and PP, and the emergence and increasing popularity of new challenger parties. As a result, the government majority and even government stability have been undermined. Between 2011 and 2019 five elections were held and three challenger parties entered the parliament, the far left Podemos, the liberal Ciudadanos, and the populist right Vox. As they are new parties it is hard to draw far-reaching conclusions about their parliamentary behaviour. Still it seems that some of them have their share in stabilising governments with ideological proximity. Ciudadanos, entered the parliament in 2016, when the legislature just lasted a few months, but from 2016 to 2018 it was the formal supporter of the conservative minority government. In this context, its low activity in Parliament can be deemed as responsible in the sense of facilitating government action as it was close to the executive on the political landscape. Podemos eventually became, after two consecutive elections that resulted in a significant electoral growth of the far right, one of the supporters of the Socialists by 2019.

The responsibility of opposition parties in Spain must be also placed along the territorial dimension. Overall, the Canary Island regional group and the Basque PNV are contributing less to policy making. The high levels of political and fiscal autonomy of the Basque country and the insularity of the Canary Islands well explain their low performance (Palau and Muñoz, 2018). In contrast, the Catalan groups, ERC and CIU, introduce a higher proportion of bills, which demonstrates their higher incentives to influence Spanish politics. Yet, it is worth mentioning that ERC willingness to contribute to policy has significantly decreased in

⁵Data source: all the data for the Spanish case comes from Q-Dem research project (www.q-dem.com).

recent legislatures (from 6.8 bills per MP in the first Zapatero legislature [2004–2008] to 1.1 in the 2016–2018 period).⁶ Whether this decline is explained by the Catalan secessionist process or is also related to governability problems in the last legislatures is something that deserves further investigation as the performance of other parliamentary groups also declined.

From the above experiences, some patterns of opposition responsibility can be identified. Overall, opposition behaviour is structured by political realities, party strategic goals and institutional constraints/opportunities. Responsibility—conceptualised here as performance—unfolds on these grounds in complex ways. A fundamental political reality was the economic crisis. Both in Italy and Spain opposition responsibility during the crisis years can be clearly observed. In Italy, it resulted in the responsibility among most mainstream opposition forces that first established a technocratic government and then a grand coalition. In Spain, the relative vulnerability of the minority governments increased opposition performance levels. This was the case during the crisis period as well. Nevertheless, it should be noted that this higher activity level of most opposition parties in Spain was not destructive rather it served the fulfilment of their party strategic goals to develop potential influence. This was particularly the case with the mainstream conservative PP that sympathised with the measures that the Socialist government had to introduce at that time. As contrast, the populist opposition Fidesz in Hungary refrained either from developing cooperative strategies or promoting own party policy aims or even fighting for immediate political advantage, that is office. The partisan strategic goal, namely to demolish the rival Socialists and get to power after that overruled other considerations. The assumed dividing line between temporary opposition parties and permanent opposition parties prevalent in academic literature becomes blurred due to Fidesz' behaviour in which neither policy consideration nor broader polity related considerations seem to matter.

In several instances, differences in performance do not necessarily connect to differences in responsibility. For example, in Spain under the majority conservative PP government (2011–2016) the opposition performance significantly declines while in Hungary both the far right and the green opposition parties (Jobbik and LMP, respectively) perform excessively under the qualified majority populist Fidesz government post-2010. It was more important for the latter two new parties to make themselves visible than to consider the lack of their impact in face of the two-third government majority or observe their limited resources—in contrast to our propositions in the theoretical frame. In other instances, the findings would need further and deeper insight. For example, in Italy despite the expectation that more policy-focused behaviour would follow on the evolving bipolar and then three-polar party-political scene we have found higher level of

⁶CIU has not its own parliamentary group in the Spanish parliament since 2016.

scrutiny activity at the detriment of policy activity. This has probably to do with the newcomer status of some specific political actors (as, mainly, in the case of the M5S). The newcomer parties tend to perform on a higher level, but this is often qualified by the party populist or non-populist placement as well as by their size. Larger populists in Italy and Hungary certainly undervalue the representative institution when in opposition. This confirms previous empirical evidence that the biggest parties perform poorly when in opposition as compared to the smallest ones (De Giorgi and Ilonszki, 2018).

In Spain and post-2010 Hungary, strong policy focus features the opposition—although its sources are different: institutional opportunities due to minority governments in Spain while the new parties' strong intention to gain policy visibility in Hungary. Opposition performance must be clearly evaluated by the constraints imposed by formal rules and regulations. As noted in the theory section, introducing a significant number of bills only pays if they really get attention as working alternatives. In Spain and Hungary opposition bills must pass a vote in the Chamber, which results in most initiatives dying at the beginning of the legislative process. In these political systems, policy-related performance can rarely be used as obstruction. This is not the case in Italy, where there are no formal procedural constraints on bills sponsorships by opposition MPs, although only a tiny minority of private members' bills are than included in the parliamentary agenda (De Micheli and Verzichelli, 2004). The scrutiny activity in Spain is also limited by definition because the number of questions and of interpellations that can be introduced by parliamentary groups is restricted by formal rules and mainly depends on their number of seats (Chaqués-Bonafont et al., 2015). The rules of the game affect opposition behaviour and their capacity to perform.

Overall, it has been confirmed that most opposition parties retain interest in performing in parliament (Helms, 2008). In terms of responsibility, some contributed to stabilising the national polity although were not particularly efficient in the policy game (Italy). In other instances, despite occasional cooperative efforts (supporting executive form outside) and strong policy focus they could not or could only modestly add to the solution of the pressing problem namely a well working parliament-government framework (Spain). As for Hungary, the most stressing finding is the sharp difference between pre- and post-2010 opposition responsibility patterns, showing that a large populist party in opposition (Fidesz) has different considerations both in terms of power and responsibility than smaller populist forces.

2.2 *Quality check*

Opposition parties' activities that we call quality check include actions to preserve the fundamental functions of parliament and, more broadly, support the norms

of responsible parliamentary government. As mentioned in the theory section, in terms of performance opposition action while in terms of quality check opposition reaction is expectedly more pronounced. The extent of government pressure and the institutional opportunities available for the opposition will largely explain opposition behaviour in this regard. These aspects are dynamic as government composition, government type and ambition also vary—with implications on opposition behaviour.

Government actions that might raise quality concerns can connect to both policy-making and scrutiny. As to the former, overwhelming urgency measures and the overload of government orders (or decree laws) can substantially curtail opposition opportunities. The shortened time for the discussion of the bills and excessive government action justifies concerns regarding responsible government. As for scrutiny tightened disciplinary measures and the neglect of scrutiny institutions can be signs that government excessive action challenges assumed responsibility.

In Hungary, the share of bills legislated under special urgency measures was high—around one-third—in the 2006–2010 parliament, this being the instrument for the minimal winning and minority governments to pursue the increasingly crisis triggered policy aims. Nevertheless, the ‘quasi expert’ government in 2009–2010 used the smallest proportion of this measure. The post-2010 two-third qualified majority governments did not need that instrument so much, they used other measures to pursue their political agenda. For example, close to 40% of enacted bills were private member bills (all from the government benches) between 2010 and 2014 which constrained the normal discussion of these bills; or nearly half of the bills post-2018 were omnibus bills, that is a mix without a clear policy profile. The average time for committee sittings decreased from close to 3 h in 2006–2010 to just one hour in the 2014–2018 term. Both the plenary and the committee sittings emptied, and opposition became deprived of these forums.

It can be rightly claimed that a responsible opposition—whose concern is responsible for parliamentary democracy—is expected to step forward under these conditions. An interesting move in opposition party behaviour was that in the 2014–2018 term they began to develop cooperative strategies despite their diverse political profile—although without positive outcome. The proposed investigation committee jointly similarly to so-called debate days. At these occasions they gave publicity to important policy issues like land privatisation, education, emigration and corruption among others. The opposition—despite their widely different ideological placement and policy profile—in most quality check measures acted in unison. Government pressure and the neglect of opposition by them escalated into a situation by the end of 2018 that opposition party MPs first tried to boycott parliamentary legislation at the plenary and afterwards went into the building

of the public television to read their proclamation, that is to inform the public about the serious democracy deficits of parliamentary decision-making. In the end, they could not read the proclamation.⁷ It seems that in face of the constraints the opposition was unable to fulfil its parliamentary duties as expected according to the norms of representative and responsible parliamentary government and first tried to turn to obstruction and then to extra-parliamentary measures—without effect. Excessive government action could not be healed by excessive opposition action. The government responded with increased disciplinary measures against MPs and the public remained mostly silent.

In a sense, significant political ‘turbulences’ have also affected the evolution of the role and behaviour of opposition in Italy. As said above, a long-lasting transition towards a quasi bi-polar party system has characterised the so-called second Republic, at least since 1994. In this period, the academic and political debate on the transformation of parliamentary functions has focused on the evolution of a new, ‘complete’ mode that would incorporate responsive representation and responsible orientation in government duties (De Giorgi, 2016). This alleged evolution, however, remained largely partial. On the one hand, fluidity and fragmentation have remained the most pronounced features of the Italian party system, that has not only weakened government coalitions and (mainly) the executives, but that has also constrained and penalised the evolution of a ‘mature’ opposition. The attitude of both majority and opposition parties to form separate groups once in parliament even when they had presented common electoral lists, could be mentioned as a clear evidence of this dynamics. On the other hand, there has not been a real and consistent political will to institutionalise the role of the opposition (for instance formalising a statute governing the right and prerogatives of the opposition). There has not been any real reform of the parliamentary standing orders in this direction in the last 20 years, although the opportunity of ‘harmonising’ the parliamentary settings, recognising a new role for the opposition, was felt as a necessity by many observers and political actors (De Giorgi, 2016). There have been some attempts (no more than bills presented to the parliament indeed), promoted by opposition parties, in this direction. But they were not supported by a clear political willingness, and by the ability to contemporary promote the necessary constitutional reforms (Lupo, 2009), nor the opposition parties have ever shown and developed a common position or strategy in this regard.

Moreover, ordinary procedures have been literally evaded by the executives, in favour of ‘extra-ordinary’ legislative procedures such as decree laws, that have well exceeded the 55% of the bills sent to the parliament by the executives (excluding bills ratifying international treaties) in the last three legislative terms, or

⁷Eventually the MPs were thrown out of the building and some beaten up by security guards.

the use of the motion of confidence, that has reached a ratio of more than 0.62 confidence votes per bills (once again excluding bills ratifying international treaties) with the Renzi government in 2016 (Marangoni and Verzichelli, 2018b).

There has been a more recent attempt to reform the constitution, promoted by the Renzi government in 2014, that mainly involved a significant transformation of the bicameral structure of the Italian parliament. The attempted constitutional reform has characterised the parliamentary debates for almost two years with the intense participation of the opposition parties which showed differentiated attitudes, however. The two extremes were represented by the search for collaboration by FI (at least initially) on the one hand, and the total and absolute rejection of any kind of cooperation by the M5S on the other hand, with the NL and parties from the extreme left showing a somehow intermediate attitude (Marangoni and Verzichelli, 2018a). Typical dynamics of politics and political (and electoral) competition, however, have at the end prevailed over the discussion on the content of the reform and over the search of the best institutional solutions. This has been largely due to the high politicisation of the issue that has resulted into an harsh referendum campaign in 2016, that has seen majority and minority parties in opposite camps, the eventual rejection of the reform at the same referendum (with a 60% of voters saying 'no' to the reform).

Talking about quality check in the case of Spain, it is necessary to emphasise, that as mentioned above the Spanish parliament has been subjected in the last two terms to a de facto institutional deadlock because of the difficulties to reach the necessary parliamentary majorities. The behaviour of all parties can be deemed as non-responsible in the sense of not facilitating the normal functioning of the parliamentary institution. While nationalist parties facilitated stable majorities during the nineties this stopped short in our observation period. Still, it seems that responsibility can develop under pressure. Following the April 2019 elections, the disagreement between the PSOE and Podemos on how to deal with the Catalan problem new elections had to be called that resulted in the loss of seats for both parties and an unprecedented growth of the extreme right (VOX). The day after the elections the Socialists and Podemos announced the formation of a coalition government that was facilitated by the abstention of ERC, the Catalan secessionist party, at the investiture process in January 2020.

Due to parliamentary deadlock normal parliamentary procedures have often been bypassed, with the neglect of opposition rights. However, opposition discontent with the decision-making style goes back to the economic crisis period, when the Spanish Constitution was reformed imposing limits on public expenditure with urgent procedure, without referendum and without any parliamentary debate. Furthermore, the crisis resulted into an increasing use of decree-laws (Chaqués-Bonafont et al., 2015). In 2012, the percentage of decree-laws represented 54% of the total legislation passed, and only 34% of these decrees were

later processed as bills guaranteeing opposition rights. This pattern continues, and is especially important since 2016, so it cannot be attributed only to the crisis. From 2016 to 2019, decree laws represented 70%, 62%, 64% and 68% of the total legislation passed in Spain. The percentage of these decree laws that were later processed as bills is 0%, 24%, 71% and 11%, respectively, so generally, opposition rights are not respected. The use of non-ordinary procedures to pass legislation has also significantly increased, especially since 2008. The government increasingly abuses the decentralised procedure, which allows the bill to pass from the Committee stage to the Senate without a previous plenary debate and vote, thus reducing the capacity of opposition groups to express their opinion on the plenary floor.⁸ Before 2007 the use of this procedure rarely reached above 50% of the total legislation passed. In 2008, it was used in 68% of the legislation passed, and since then it has continued increasing, sometimes also combined with the urgency procedure, reaching in 2019, 83% of legislation passed. Overall, it seems that parliamentary gridlock has been used by the government to pass important policy reforms skipping the parliamentary regular procedure in a significant number of initiatives.

All this did not go unnoticed on the part of opposition groups. On the one hand, they strongly criticised the executive's governing style in both the parliamentary and the media arena. On the other hand, since 2016 a significant number of reforms in the standing orders aimed to improve the quality of the parliamentary institution: to increase the transparency of the Chamber, facilitate public access to parliamentary data and information. Finally, there has been also a significant increase in the number of investigation committees. From 2016 to 2019, five investigation Committees were created, the highest number ever in the democratic period. However, most of these Committees' decisions are not binding, often have a purely political goal and respond to party strategies or reflect the will of the parliamentary majority, so they have been criticised as instruments of effective parliamentary control and as instruments to improve the quality of the parliamentary institution.

We expected that regarding quality check the reaction component of opposition parties would be more important as they largely reflect on increased government pressure. Nevertheless, pro-action can also be observed, as both in Spain and Italy opposition aimed for parliamentary procedural reform when the governments were weak either for institutional or political reasons, and in Hungary opposition parties worked out joint strategies in face of increased government pressure. We have also found one important difference between the performance aspect and the quality check aspect of opposition responsibility. Regarding the

⁸Parliamentary Committees do not facilitate the express of opposition because they are dominated by the parliamentary majority.

former the party differences are more pronounced mainly because—as explained in the conclusive part of the performance section—individual party strategies have impact on these performance patterns. As a contrast in terms of quality check opposition interest is more unified and individual party considerations have a lesser role.

3. Conclusions

Critiques might claim that we ‘expect’ too much from the opposition when we place the burden of responsibility on them as opposition obviously works under serious constraints. Indeed, these constraints feature parliamentary government, including executive prominence embodied by legislative advantage and diverse standing rule measures. Nevertheless, we were able to detect nuances and even patterns of opposition responsibility both in relation to their performance—partially but not exclusively tied to strict parliamentary measures—and in relation to their quality check steps. Overall, we can conclude that opposition responsibility unfolds around how government responsibility is performed and around opposition partisan strategic goals.

We have found a variety of considerate opposition action in performance or under-performance or even excessive performance, in government formation or in attempts to stabilise the polity. Of course, we have identified several non-responsible actions.

We have also identified a paradox. While a certain level of opposition independence ensured by parliamentary rules and by extra-parliamentary democratic standards is necessary for responsible behaviour, increasing pressure does not seem to curtail opposition responsibility. Nevertheless, under excessive government action opposition must pay a bigger price to be able to pursue responsible behaviour: they have to use more resources with regard to the performance aspect or suffer more disciplinary measures with regard to the quality check aspect to be able to pursue their expected partisan cum opposition functions and do it responsibly.

At the beginning of this article, we formulated some expectations that also need reflection here. We have basically found that permanent opposition parties do not show less responsible action. First, it is increasingly difficult to find parties permanently in opposition (Italy) or those that have been permanently in opposition like regional parties or IU (later Podemos) in Spain or Jobbik in Hungary—although representing two edges of the political spectrum—have shown substantial responsibility steps either in government stabilisation or in quality check.

As a contrast populist opposition parties’ responsibility is more varied: in Hungary, low level of action and non-responsibility featured Fidesz but not at all Jobbik; in Italy, limited performance is only partly true as NL and M5S have been

relatively less active in bills sponsorships but focus their activity on parliamentary scrutiny. In Spain, the far right populist opposition parties just recently entered the Spanish parliament so we cannot draw conclusions about them in this regard. So far, we could not confirm that new parties show less responsible behaviour. The entry of new opposition parties in parliament following the 2015 elections ended bipartisanship trends and hampered government formation leading to new elections few months later. Yet, Ciudadanos behaved responsibly facilitating government formation during the Rajoy legislature in 2016.

It is more controversial to identify the impact of opposition polarisation on their responsibility. In Hungary in contrast to our anticipation in the introduction on the negative impact of opposition fragmentation and polarisation the maturing of opposition responsibility can be observed, including some cooperative inter-party opposition strategies. In Italy, this expectation is also false in terms of performance measures but the lack of a clear and common political strategy has in a sense hindered the possibility to reform parliamentary settings and rules, acknowledging and institutionalising a new role for parliamentary minority. Also, in Spain, divided opposition fosters electoral competition and short-term strategies thus hinder the development of broader responsibility patterns. While nationalist parties had traditionally provided support to minority governments thus fostering stability, Spanish politics has moved in the last decade towards political polarisation around the territorial dimension, moving Spanish politics from consensus to increasing polarisation and confrontation increasing the complexity of feasible political alliances.

We can conclude that rich variation can be observed on opposition responsibility behaviour patterns. These are country specific, as well as party specific. This confirms the context-driven nature and understanding of responsibility. The analysis—and the recurring presence and visibility—of opposition responsibility overarched the pre-crisis, the crisis and post-crisis year demonstrating the relevance of the theme. In several instances, the opposition could not have an impact while in other instances implicitly it could influence political developments for good. A healthy parliamentary democracy requires both responsible government and responsible opposition and both must be carefully analysed.

Funding

The authors did not receive any funding for the production of this study.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors have no conflicts of interest to report.

Acknowledgements

G.I. thanks the support of the Hungarian national research fund NKIF project number 12883 that made this research possible. A.M.P. would like to thank the support of Project La Oposición Política en España: Estrategias en la Arena Parlamentaria (RTI2018-096950-A-I00) funded by the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities (Spain).

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